

April, and high parasitism in May and August suggest that parasitoid activity might not be dependent on the density

of egg masses in the field. Sterility in borer egg masses was caused by high temperature, particularly in May. Many

parasitoids could not emerge from eggs when the air temperature was higher than 32°C. ■

Insecticide dusts provide only short-term control of whitebacked planthoppers

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A high population of the whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) in rice at Telok Chengai offered an opportunity to evaluate the effects of various dust insecticide formulations. In Malaysia, farmers use 1% propoxur dust and 2% MTMC + 2% phenthoate dust for control of brown planthopper. The dust is delivered by a motorized knapsack blower fixed with a 30-m multihole vinyl tube. The system speeds the treatment of affected fields.

The first set of experiments was conducted on 21 May 1979. Thirty hills per field were sampled with a portable suction sampler. The three dusts tested effectively reduced the population of WBPH nymphs and adults. The population remained low for about a week. But 2 weeks after the treatment, WBPH density increased in all treatments (see figure). In fact, the population in the treated fields was higher than the original, possibly due to immigration. The dusts appeared toxic to the WBPH predator *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, which unlike WBPH, did not increase rapidly after treatment. The dusts' effect on spiders was similar to that on

C. lividipennis.

In another experiment with 2% MIPC dust on 16 June 1979, 20 hills were

examined visually; the results were similar to those of the earlier experiments. ■

Relative attraction of rice hoppers and their common predators to different light sources

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In Malaysia, light traps attracted particularly high populations of rice leafhoppers and planthoppers during massive hopper outbreaks in 1967 in

Trengganu, in 1977 in Tanjong Karang, and in 1979 in Kedah. As many as 92.16 million brown planthoppers (BPH) may be caught by 15 fluorescent lamp traps between 1900 and 2330 hours. Subsequent studies showed that intensive light trapping rapidly destroyed large BPH populations in an outbreak; as many as 141 BPH/hill may be removed by 1 trap/0.4-ha area. Because increased trapping efficiency could remove more BPH, the relative attractiveness of different light sources was studied.

Four sources of light were compared — a 25-watt black light, a 25-watt fluorescent light, a 60-watt tungsten light, and light from a kerosene pressure lamp (Butterfly) operating at maximum pressure. The traps were set 1.8 m above the ground and at least 228.5 m apart. They were set up simultaneously for 3 nights (24, 27, and 28 Feb 1978) from 1800 to 2200 hours.

Black light had the greatest attraction. Based on the overall catch per source, the catch efficiency of black light was about

Insects (mean no./trap per night)

Catches of rice leafhoppers and their common predators by light traps of different light sources. B = black light, F = fluorescent light, T = tungsten light, K = kerosene pressure lamp.

Catches of rice hoppers and their common predators by light traps of different light sources.

Light source	Catches (%)					
	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	<i>Nephrotettix spp.</i>	<i>Cyrtorhinus lividipennis</i>	<i>Paederus fuscipes</i>	<i>Casnoidea interstitialis</i>
Black light (25 W)	74.2	88.8	66.4	77.9	89.3	74.2
Fluorescent light (25 W)	16.7	2.1	17.8	7.3	6.9	19.4
Tungsten light (60 W)	2.6	1.3	6.1	10.3	1.9	1.9
Kerosene pressure lamp	6.5	7.8	9.7	4.5	1.9	4.5

9 times that of fluorescent light, 20 times that of the kerosene pressure lamp, and 24 times that of tungsten light (see figure). The catches of the three other light sources were not significantly different ($P > 0.05$). The trend was the same for insect species studied individually.

Black light attracted more than 74% of each of the insect species studied except *Nephrotettix* spp., and 89.3% of the predator *Paederus fuscipes* (see table). Among the three other light sources, the fluorescent light caught the most insects. But the catch was always lower than 20% of the total catch of each species.

Although the use of black light can tremendously increase light-trap

efficiency in rice fields, it has some practical limitations at the farm level. The most notable is the need for electric current and the possible hazard to eyesight on close exposure. Nevertheless, black light deserves further study because of its high capacity to attract and,

therefore, its potential usefulness in destroying massive pest populations during outbreaks. Its possible farm use to monitor insect species, prevent pest buildup, or remove huge populations of highly phototoxic insect pests should be studied. ■

Feeding behavior of *Dicladispa armigera*

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A single *Dicladispa armigera* (Oliv.) grub was found to consume 20 to 410 (av 132.4) mm² of rice leaf area in its lifetime. From 1 to 10 (av 4.7) larval

mines/leaf were found. After emergence the adult beetles began to feed mostly at the apical parts of leaves and proceeded downward. The adult beetles produced parallel white membranous streaks by scraping the chlorophyll of leaves. The length of streaks ranged from 1 to 78 mm (av 7.6 mm). A single adult beetle consumed 6.2 to 54.5 (av 25.3) mm² of leaf area/day. The severely infested leaf